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Gender Taxonomy in Select Sanskrit Texts

Dr. Priya Jose K, Dr. P. K. Sreekumar¹

Abstract

The ancient Indian mind freely pursued many branches of knowledge. It showed keen interest in matters of sex as proven by the vast body of literature written on the art of love. The present paper analyses three texts; *Ratirahasya* attributed to Kokkoka, *Anangaranga* of Kalyanamalla and *Śṛṅgāramañjarī* written by the Muslim saint Akbar Shah dealing with the subject of erotics. These texts are noted for the elaborate treatment of the subject. What is noticeable is the minute classification of the male and female types according to physical and sexual characteristics.

Keywords: *Ratirahasya*, *Śṛṅgāramañjarī*, *Anangaranga*, classification, women

Kama which includes love, desire, pleasure, music, good food, perfume, the fine life is one of the Purusharthas according to the Indian system. The rest of the trivarga are Dharma and Artha. Each of them is the subject of a science or sastra embodied in a number of texts. The subject of sex finds mention in Rgveda, Atharvaveda, the Upanishads and in the Mahabharata. Apart from the iconic text *Kamasutra* of Vatsyayana there is a sizable body of work written on erotics. Kokkoka in his work *Ratirahasya* mentions his predecessors Gonikaputra, Munindra, Munibhih, Karnisuta, Muladeva, Gunapataka, Vatsyayana, Muni, Nagarjuna, Shabdarnava, Hamekhala, Uddisha, Yogavali, Munindra and Munayah. *Śṛṅgāramañjarī* the seventeenth century Sanskrit-Telugu treatise on love attributed to the polymath Muslim saint Akbar Shah refers to a good number of works in Telugu and Sanskrit: *Rasamanjari*, *Amoda*, *Parimala*, *Srngaratilaka*, *Rasikapriya*, *Rasarnava*, *Prataparudriya*, *Sundarasringara*, *Narasakavya*, *Dasarupaka*, *Vilasaratnakara*,

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Kavyapariksa, *Dasarupaka*, *Vilasaratnakara*, *Kavyapariksa* and *Kavyaprakasa*. *Ananga Ranga* of Kalyana Malla in addition to other popular and canonical texts mention *Panchasayaka*, *Smarapradipa*, *Ratimanjari* and *Manasollasa*. From this list it is evident that a vast body of literature on erotics was present in both Sanskrit and vernacular. These texts are replete with minute classification of the male and female types and deserve a detailed study by social scientists. The present paper attempts to describe the classification of the male and female types as seen in the works *Ratirahasya*, *Anangaranga* and *Śṛṅgāramañjarī*. A short introduction to these works would be pertinent at this juncture.

Śṛṅgāramañjarī

V. Raghavan, a reputed scholar who headed the department of Sanskrit at the University of Madras discovered two manuscripts—one is Sanskrit and the other in Telegu—of *Śṛṅgāramañjarī* in the 1940s. By comparing and collating the versions he was able to plug lacunae and reconstruct a text complete except for a few lines at the end. The authorship of this work falls on Akbar Shah alias Saint Sayyid Shah Kalimullah Husain also known as Bade Sahib. He was a descendant to Bande Nawaz Hazarat, the renowned Muslim saint Gesu Daraz of Gulbarga. His proper name was Sardar-ud-Din Muhammed Husain but was commonly called Muhammed Gesu Daraz, on account of his having long ringlets (Raghavan 4). Just like his illustrious forbear, Akbar Shah too began to be venerated as a saint or ouliah in the Islamic fashion after his premature death. It was, and is, not uncommon among Muslims, especially in its more popular and indigenous manifestations, to venerate deceased saintly personalities, but it can plausibly be argued that given the high degree of cultural symbiosis and synthesis that characterized the seventeenth century Hyderabad, a Muslim saint was a common phenomenon, transcending the barriers of caste and creed. There are many grounds to problematize the assumed authorship of Akbar Shah. To take a textual evidence, one may suspect the likelihood of a practicing Muslim having composed a work with an undisguised invocation to muses, gods and goddesses of a polytheistic belief system, but given the unusual degree of synthesis and syncretism already referred to, one may argue that there is nothing inherently improbable in Akbar

Shah's writing hymns adulating, exulting and praising deities and his preceptor. It may more legitimately be doubted whether a Muslim saint would write a work on mundane love in Sanskrit and Telugu. However, it is a fact that Buddhist and Jains have written treatises on love (Raghavan 7). The *Śṛṅgāramañjarī* is closely related to two previous works—the *Rasamanjari* of Bhanudatta and a commentary on it called the *Amoda*. It generally criticizes the former and adopts many of the views expressed in the latter.

Anangaranga

Translated as *The Stage of Love*, the work was composed by the poet Kalyanamalla, for the amusement of Ladkhan, the son of Ahmed Lodi, the same Ladkhan being in some places spoken of as Ladana Mull, and in others as Ladanaballa. He is supposed to have been a relation or connection of the house of Lodi, which reigned in India from A.D. 1450 to 1526. The work would therefore, have been written in the fifteenth or sixteenth century. It contains ten chapters, and has been translated into English but only six copies were printed for private circulation. This is supposed to be the latest of the Sanskrit works on the subject, and the ideas in it were evidently taken from previous writings of the same nature remarks Mulk Raj Anand in his Prelude to *Kamasutra* (52). This treatise has been translated to almost all the languages. "In Arabic, Hindostani and the Moslem dialects, the *Anangaranga* becomes Lizzat al-Nisa, or the Pleasures of Women; and it appears with little change in Persian and Turkish" (*Anangaranga* xi).

Ratirahasya

In the available literature on Kama Sastra in Sanskrit, the *Ratirahasya* believed to have been written between A.D. 830 and 960 is next in importance only to the text of Vatsyayana. In fact, it may be said to have gained greater popularity because of its concise treatment opines Raghavan in his Foreword to the text (vii). Indeed, in many Indian languages, the name of its author Koka or Kokkoka has become a synonym of the subject Kama Sastra itself. He has been known in several names like Kokkaka, Kokkoka, Kokka, Koka, Kukkoka, Kupkoka, Koka-deva, Koka Pandita, and so on (*Ratirahasya* 8). The popularity of Kokkoka is borne out also by the fact that the text was translated into Persian (vi). Kokkoka wrote

the *Ratirahasya* to satisfy the curiosity of King Vainyadatta (9). The author's main objective appears to instruct men in the art of winning over frigid women, or those suffering from sexual anaesthesia. He particularly stresses the methods by which a man may not only gain the attention of women, but in due course, may come to sustain their affections. To achieve this ambitious objective, Kokkoka made a thorough study of the works of his predecessors, both in the field of Erotics as well as in other ancillary topics. The aim of Kokkoka is not merely to give us a compendium of the subject, but to bring into prominence the ideas of writers other than Vatsyayana. The study naturally takes the form of classifications and enumerations which are but names of the psychological variations in men and women. It is immensely helpful in understanding the types of characters etc. as dealt with in the different texts of Kama Sastra literature. S. A. Upadhyay remarks

In 552 artistic strophies, composed in different metres and divided into fifteen chapters, *Ratirahasya* elucidates almost every aspect of its subject; the well-known fourfold classification of females and their distinct characteristics, the ways and means of winning them over, the different erogenous zones, the classification of males and females, the twenty-seven types of union, females of different provinces and their sexual characteristics, details of tumescence and detumescence, the vivacious variety of postures, on acquiring a wife, use of agents for enticing other women, etc. The prescription of different Mantras and rites of enticing women helps us to understand the Tantric practices as in vogue. The aphrodisiacs described in 130 stanzas in the last chapter reveal the progress in Indian medicine. (*Ratirahasya* xviii) Kokkoka classified women into four major categories—Padmini, Sāṅkhini, Citriṇi, Hastini; tabulated their physical, psychological and sexual characteristics, along with the days and nights and Yamas thereof and postures favourable for each of them for the attainment of the highest conjugal happiness. Some contend that this classification has been lifted from Vatsyayana: in actual fact, it is conspicuously absent in the Kama Sutra.

Classification of Women

Padmini

Ratirahasya mentions that she has a slim, fragrant body soft as a Lotus; eyes red at the end like those of timid fawn; breasts like bilva fruit, fine nose like sesame flower. She can be dark like lily or fair

like Campaka and possesses soft graceful swan like gait. She is swan throated, finely dressed, devout, bashful and preserves her self respect. She only consumes soft, pure, light food; likes white dress and flowers. Her private parts resemble an opening lotus bud and fluid has Lotus smell. The Padmansana pose and the last quarter of the night are suitable for her. *Śṛṅgāramañjarī* echoes the same. *Anangaranga* describes her moon like face, soft like Sirisa flower and fine neck. She is the best type of woman and is considerate.

Sāṅkhini

Ratirahasya describes her as stout or lean, tall; long legs, nerves and veins prominent in her tall, slim body, having many hollows (owing to absence of flesh). She has the voice of an ass, is irascible, fault finding and not pure in mind. She has a heated and bilious constitution; likes red garments and flowers; eats neither more nor less. She has very hairy private parts; meagre saltish smelling fluid. She scratches with nails in enjoyment. *Anangaranga* notes her meagre breast, tawny complexion and pitiless nature. The suitable pose and time for her is the Venu- darita pose and third quarter of night. Bilva fruit mixed with the root of the fragrant Tagara and a special mantra will entice her. *Śṛṅgāramañjarī* describes her as very loving, devoted to her lord. It adds that she wears jewels with blue stones.

Citrīṇi

Ratirahasya describes her as slim, neither too tall nor too short and with graceful gait. She has broad breasts and loins; prominent lip, conch like neck; voice similar to that of cakora. Adept and devoted to music, dance, painting etc, she has quick glances. She eats sweet dishes and also very little. *Anangaranga* notes her affectionate nature, dark hair and voice like that of a Peacock. Her sexual characteristics mention profuse fluid like honey and private parts soft, round, bloated and not very hairy. Nagara pose and the the first quarter of the night suitable are for her. Plantain, jati nut and a mantra will entice this type of woman who loves external sport, embrace, kissing etc. *Śṛṅgāramañjarī* also mentions her fondness of perfume and that she has a small mouth.

Hastini

Whitish in complexion, her physical features include tawny hair, short and stout neck, thick and dangling lips, big and crooked fingers on feet,

stuttering in speech, immense size, and slow, graceless gait. She likes red garments and ornaments. She has a bilious constitution and wants many men. The smell of her body is similar to elephant's ichor. She is a heavy eater who eats hot, acrid and astringent food. Very difficult to gratify sexually, her sexual characteristics list reddish fluid smelling similar to elephants icor, hairy and very broad private parts. *Anangaranga* calls her severe and cruel. The skandha- pada- yugala pose and the second quarter of the night are the suitable time for her. She can be captivated by the ash of the wings of the dove and bee mixed with honey and administered with Pansupari and a separate mantra. *Śṛṅgāramañjarī* records the additional feature that her mating time is the first quarter of the night which does not agree with the time given either in *Ratirahasya* or *Anganaranga*.

Analysis

The Padmini, evidently, is the best type of woman and the elaboration of her features is all based on this single idea of her being the best type and being comparable to the lotus, her leading characteristic is not only beauty but delicateness. Citriṇi comes next in point of merit. Her chief accomplishment and variety of tastes and flashy behaviour, is based on the word citra meaning 'manifold' and 'striking'. A careful scrutiny of Sāṅkhini would show that we have to underlie the statement in the *Ratirahasya* and other texts that her nerves and veins are visible on her frame, that she is devoid of flesh, and that her body is full of hollows. As Sankha means shell and bone, she is to be understood as the fleshless woman. Hastini by all description stands lowest in the order, she is, as her name suggests, the heavy corpulent type. (*Śṛṅgāramañjarī*, Raghavan 42)

Vatsyayana's Classification of Women and Men

Vatsyayana's classification of women and men into Harini, Vadava, Hastini and Shasha, Vrisha and Ashva, according to the parinaha (circumference) and the ayama (length, depth) of their respective organs is followed in these texts too. There are three kinds of men, namely, the Shasha, or the Hare-man; the Vrishabha, or Bull-man, and the Ashwa, or Horse-man. These divisions again appear to represent the nervous, bilious and sanguine temperament.

Harini

The deer type of woman has a shapely head with a thick and wavy

growth of hair, a small belly, protruding posteriors, small nostrils, large and beautiful eyes adorned with long lashes. Her lips, palms and soles are reddish; arms straight and delicately shaped; ears, cheeks and neck long, and her abdomen and thighs are not unduly fat. Her ankles are symmetrical, and her gait is like that of an elephant in rut. Her breasts are firm and prominent, although her frame is delicate. She has a gentle nature, betrays little anger, but can be greatly perturbed by envy. She eats moderately, but entertains a fondness for physical unions. Her fluid has the fragrance of a flower, her fingers are straight and her speech pleasant. Her yoni is deep, and measures six angulas. Her build is quite erect and her nature affectionate.

Vadava

The mare type of woman possesses an unshapely head (not well-rounded); thick and oily hair; quivering eyes, like the petals of a blue lotus: and her ears and face are broad and long. Her teeth are large and strong; her lips long; her breasts full and firm like water-pitchers; arms strong but graceful; belly small, and hands soft as a lotus. Her chest is wide, her speech is pleasantly halting. She is greatly perturbed by jealousy. Her navel is deep and round, her abdomen is asymmetrical but pleasing, her thighs even and short. Her waist is broad, and she leans from the middle. Her walk is leisurely and coquettish, her feet are symmetrical and pink; her mind is wavering; her body delicate. She is fond of eating and sleeping, and is given to day-dreaming about her lover. She is disposed to phlegm and wind, and her fluid is yellowish and smells like flesh. She has a strong libido and her fluid flows easily. Her yoni measures nine angulas. (*Ratirahasya* 32)

Hastini

The elephant type of woman is characterised by broad cheeks, thick ears and nostrils. Her two palms, soles, arms and thighs are short and broad. Her neck is curved, rough, thick and dun-coloured. She entertains a continuous desire for indulging in conjugation; has a deep voice and a heavy body, like an elephant's. Her lips are long and drooping, and her fluid flows profusely. She has an irritable temperament, displays a yellowish hue in her eyes and her fluid smells like that of an elephant in rut. She is also given to sinning

surreptitiously. She has many deficiencies and she is usually won over forcibly by the use of the rod. Her yoni measures about twelve angulas.

The Shasha

The Hare-man is known by Linga which in erection does not exceed six finger-breadths, or about three inches. His figure is short and spare, but well-proportioned in shape and make. He has small hands, knees, feet, loins and thighs, the latter being darker than the rest of the skin. His features are clear and well-proportioned; his face is round, his teeth are short and fine, his hair is silky, and his eyes are large and well-opened. He is of quiet disposition, does good for virtue's sake and looks forward to making name. He is humble in demeanour; his appetite for food is small, and he is moderate in carnal desires. Finally, there is nothing offensive in his Kama-salila or semen.

The Vrishabha

The Bull-man, is known by Linga of nine fingers in length, or four inches and a half. His body is robust and tough, like that of tortoise. His chest is fleshy and belly hard. His forehead is high, his eyes large and long, with pink corners, and the palms of his hands are red. His disposition is cruel and violent, restless and irascible, and his Kama-salila is ever ready.

The Ashwa

The Horse-man is known by Linga of twelve fingers, or about six inches long. He is tall and large-framed, but not fleshy, and his delight is in big and robust women, never in those of delicate form. His body is hard as iron, his chest is broad, full, and muscular; his body below the hips is long, and the same is the case with his mouth and teeth, his neck and ears, whilst his hands and fingers are remarkably so. His knees are somewhat crooked, and this distortion may also be observed in the nails of his toes. His hair is long, coarse and thick. His look is fixed and hard, without changing form, and his voice is deep like that of bull. He is reckless in spirit, passionate and covetous, gluttonous, volatile, lazy, full of sleep and walks slowly. His Kama-salila is copious, salty, and goat-like.

Further Classification of Women

According to age

A woman under the age of sixteen years is classified as Bala or

maiden;thereafter, up to her thirtieth year she is Taruni or a young woman; from the thirty-first to fifty-fifth year she is Praudha or middle aged, and beyond this age she is declared Vriddha or old. Also, if a woman is tall, dark, slim and low or narrow-waisted, and indulges in unions very sparingly, she is classified as Shlatha while if a woman is fat, fair and short, broad-waisted and ever keen for unions, she is Ghana. When a woman combines some qualities from each of these two categories, she belongs to the medium category. A Bala or a maiden can be won over by the offering of betel-leaf, garlands, fruit-juice, tasty delicacies and a deferential mien, being young, she is easily pleased by the gifts of beautiful ornaments, necklaces and other trinkets.A Taruni is pleased with a sympathetic approach and a union which increases gradually in force. A Praudha harbours deep love and an emotional attachment,while a Vriddha for whom the different stages of love are over, is enchanted by sweet talk and respectful behaviour.

According to Humours

A woman whose bone-joints and ankles are not clearly visible, belongs to the phlegmatic type. Her voice is soft and sweet and she looks like a lotus.A woman whose bone-joints and ankles are clearly visible belongs to the bilious type. Her limbs are warm.A woman who is not soft, whose limbs are lukewarm and who prattles excessively belongs to the windy type(*Ratirahasya* 37).The phlegmatic woman gets the orgasm immediately; the bilious woman gets it after some time and the windy type gets it after a long time. Again,in the phlegmatic woman's yoni the fluid flows freely; the bilious yoni is very warm, and the windy type of yoni has a thick hymen. The first category again, pines for union during the Shishira or winter months and Vasanta or spring; the bilious type, during Varsha or monsoon and Sharad or autumn;the windy type during Vasanta or spring and Grishma or summer.A woman of the Shyama category possesses glistening nails, eyes and teeth. She does not repent quickly. Her gait is dignified and her attachments unwavering. The entrance to her yoni is cool, fleshy and pleasant to the touch. The Shyama type belongs to the phlegmatic class. She is the best among the three types mentioned below.Shyama does not mean dark-coloured as she means one who has reached the middle stage of youth. She is, by nature, pleasure-loving.The bilious type of woman comes next in order of preference. She has a fair complexion, large breasts, and

pinkish nails and eyes. Her sweat has an acid odour. One moment she is angry and the next moment she is happy. She favours the cold and avoids the heat. Her yoni is quite warm and loose. She is intelligent and proficient and assumes a delicate demeanour during the union. The windy type of woman is the vilest type of woman. Incessantly chattering, fond of aimless wandering, she has a dusky colour, resembling that of a slightly burnt tree. She is gluttonous; her limbs are not delicate; her hair is rough and split at the ends, while her nails and eyes are dark. She is fond of rough and forceful unions. Her yoni is as rough as a cow's tongue. When some characteristics from each of these groups overlap in a woman, she should be typed as having mixed humours.

According to Character Traits

A Devasattva woman possesses a pure and sweet-smelling body; her face is very bright. She is well-born and has many admirers. She is utterly beautiful. A Yakshasattva woman does not feel shy in the presence of elders. Her lust is easily aroused, and usually, she is anxious to enjoy unions in sylvan surroundings, drinking taverns, seaside resorts or mountain retreats. A Narasattva woman is blessed with an unassuming nature. She is gifted and hospitable, and not in the least put out by fasting. A Nagasattva woman is given to excessive sighing and yawning, and to wander-lust. She sleeps a great deal, but is never completely relaxed. A woman is declared to belong to the Gandharvasattva group when she is free from anger, accomplished in the arts of vocal and instrumental music as also in the Art of Love. She favours bright and dazzling garments and is very fond of garlands, scents and incense. The Pishachasattva woman is undignified, gluttonous and possessed of very warm limbs. She drinks intoxicating potions, eats meat. The Kakasattva woman has a constantly roving eye; she is plagued by frequent hunger-pangs and is cursed with a very fretful nature. The Vanarasattva woman has a distracted look and an unsteady mind. In love-play she is fond of fighting with the help of her teeth and nails. The Kharasattva woman indulges in contrary talk, and loves to inflict pain on her paramour during unions.

Conclusion

The list is by no means complete. There are further description of women according to the peculiarities of the regions they belong to. The classification is minute and overwhelming. Though some sound

quite unbelievable we cannot underrate the effort put into the subject from an academic and clinical point of view. It is evident that even in taxonomy the women are studied in far greater detail than the men. These works offer rules regarding the favourable types of union among the different categories mentioned above. The conclusion put forth is this: “Whether a woman is Shyama or phlegmatic or of the mare type or of the deer type; whether she belongs to the Gandharva, Yaksha, Nara or Deva-sattva type; whether she is a maiden or adorned with the beauty of growing. Youth-only one thing is of the greatest significance for the worldly mortal-that she is born with beauty solely for man’s supremest happiness”(Ratirahasya 40). It is undeniable that many of the features described of the best female type still form the basis of beauty standards to this day. We find “a sculpting of the biological body into a cultured form” in these texts (Shah 45). Hence they deserve the special attention of scholars and social scientists.

Works cited

- Anand, Mulk Raj. *Kamasutra: Ancient India in Vatsyayana’s Time*. “Prelude”. Arnold-Heinemann Publishers, New Delhi, 1982. pp 21-57.
- Ananga Ranga or *The Hindu Art of Love*. Trans. Richard Burton and Foster Fitzgerald Arbuthnot. Kamashastra Society of London and Benares, For Pvt circulation only. 1885.
- Doneiger, Wendy. *Redeeming the Kamasutra*. OUP, New York. 2016.
- Shah, Shalini. “Engendering the Material Body: A Study of Sanskrit Literature” *Social Scientist*, July-August 2019, Vol. 47, No. 7/8 (554-555) (July-August 2019), pp. 31-52.
- Srngaramanjari of Saint Akbar Shah :Based on old Sanskrit Manuscripts in Devanagari and Telugu Scripts*. Ed.V. Raghavan, Hyderabad Archeological Department Publication, 1951
- Rati Rahasya of Pandit Kokkoka: The Hindu Secrets of Love*. Trans. S. C. Upadhyaya. D. B. Taraporevala Sons. Bombay, 1965.
- The Vatsayana Kama Sutra: The Classic Translation of 1883*. Trans. Richard Burton. Kama Shastra Society of London and Benaras, For Pvt circulation, 1883.